

FUNDAMENTALS OF PROTECTING YOUTH FROM MODERN THREATS

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In today's era of globalization, spiritual threats occur in the form of attempts to change the views of certain segments of the population, especially young people, in a direction that suits them, to absorb destructive ideas such as religious extremism, immorality.

Given the fact that ideological immunity is the spiritual unity of the state and the nation, the ideological shield that protects the spiritual health, the strengthening of ideological immunity in our youth is an urgent and responsible task. Ideological immunity based on the national idea, first of all, requires that each of our compatriots has a strong faith and a high outlook. That is, the idea becomes a motivating force, a guide to action only when it occupies the human heart, when it becomes an integral part of the spiritual state of man.

Philosophy: The encyclopedic

ABSTRACT

The article examines the issues of increasing ideological immunity in opposing spiritual threats.

dictionary defines "ideological immunity - a system of ideological and theoretical views and values that serve to protect the individual, social group, nation, society from various harmful ideological influences" [3].

Immunity (Lat. Immunitas - release, escape) is a medical term, a set of reactions that are able to maintain the constant internal specificity of the organism, protect itself from various influences, the entry of external infections. In contrast to the above, if a person's general immune system is innate, it is necessary to constantly form ideological immunity.

Second, it has its own characteristics for each generation. Third, ideological inviolability in society can be ensured only when the immune system is formed [2].

The main and first element of the ideological immune system is knowledge.

However, there are many types of knowledge. Proponents of great state chauvinism and aggressive nationalist ideology also rely on certain knowledge, of course. Therefore, knowledge in the ideological immune system must be objective, accurately and fully reflect reality, enrich human spirituality and serve the development of society. By their very nature, they must be inextricably linked with the interests of the Motherland and the nation.

The second main element of the ideological immune system is the system of values formed on the basis of such advanced knowledge. Indeed, the more objective and profound the knowledge, the stronger will be the values that underlie it. The system of values determines the possibilities of ideological immunity and serves as a strong shield against harmful ideas.

The role of ideological prevention based on the system of spiritual education in the formation of the ideological immune system is great. After all, it essentially

relies on measures to prevent the infiltration of foreign ideas and to eliminate them. The system of education and advocacy promotes the implementation of ideological prevention.

The first President IA Karimov stressed the need to be vigilant, vigilant and vigilant in the face of growing threats. [1].

We can conclude that today the issues of ideological education aimed at strengthening the ideological immunity of our youth are more relevant than ever. The task of strengthening the ideological immunity of the younger generation requires the joint work of society, first of all, the family, educational institutions, the media, public organizations. As the system of continuing education is the main link in the ideological education, our educators are required to devote themselves to the development of young people who can adequately deal with destructive ideological aggression, spiritual threats.

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